

Monitoring and Evaluation Framework Tool

December 2022

RRIS2SCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

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PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	RRI2SCALE – Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy
START DATE	1 January 2020
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	https://rri2scale.eu/
COORDINATOR	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA - Italy
PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

The present document provides a template to assist local and regional authorities in setting up their monitoring and evaluation framework.

Complete the following fields to set the building blocks of your monitoring and evaluation system.

OBJECTIVES Which are the objectives and subobjectives that you aim to achieve with the whole process?

For instance, an objective can be to embed RRI in the regional governance framework. A few sub-objectives could be to (i) involve the public in decision-making; and (ii) promote science literacy.

Objective#1
• Subobjective#1.1:
• Subobjective#1.2:
• Subobjective#1.3:

MEANS Which are the best opportunities to collect feedback, and which are the most appropriate ways?

For instance, the SES session and the agenda workshop may constitute good opportunities to gather citizens' feedback. The most appropriate means range from questionnaires to interviews and focus groups.

Opportunity#1:.....	Opportunity#2:.....	Opportunity#3:.....
Mean#1:.....	Mean#2:.....	Mean#3:.....

INDICATORS Which indicators need to be monitored to measure progress towards each subobjective?

Assign a few indicators to each subobjective. Some indicators may measure the quality of the process (e.g., the quality of the discussion in a workshop), the importance of outcomes (e.g., the popularity of policy recommendations) or the change in peoples' perceptions (e.g., their attitude towards participatory processes). Also, decide which opportunity should be exploited to measure each indicator. Finally, assign a unique identifier (e.g., O1.1P#1) to each indicator.

Subobjective#1.1			
O1.1P#1	process	<i>E.g., Number of citizens believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was adequately diverse to guarantee a transdisciplinary approach and allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of citizens surveyed</i>	Opport#1
...	outcome		...
...	perception		...
Subobjective#1.2			
...	process		...

.....

EXAMPLES The following table provides examples of potential indicators.

#	Indicator
1	Number of policy-makers who reported that their participation in the SES session contributed to appreciating the positions of different citizens / Total number of policy-makers surveyed
2	Number of policy-makers who reported that their participation helped them to understand potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments) that could affect their region by 2022 and beyond / Total number of policy-makers surveyed
3	Number of policy-makers who reported a better understanding of the importance of considering ethics and social values as a measure to achieve higher acceptance of R&I-related public policies / Total number of policy-makers surveyed
4	Number of citizens who reported that their participation helped them to understand current dilemmas in their region better / Total number of citizens surveyed
5	Number of citizens believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was adequately diverse to guarantee a transdisciplinary approach and allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of citizens surveyed
6	Number of citizens who reported that they had sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to be able to participate in the discussion actively / Total number of citizens surveyed
7	Number of citizens who reported that the structure and the facilitation of the workshops allowed productive interactions between all participants and stimulated public debate / Total number of citizens surveyed
8	Number of citizens who reported that their opinions, values and expectations had a significant impact on the developed agendas and roadmaps / Total number of citizens surveyed
9	Number of citizens who reported that their participation helped them to increase their trust in regional or local authorities / Total number of citizens surveyed
10	Number of citizens who reported that in the future they would more actively take part in participatory processes for policy-making or R&I design / Total number of citizens surveyed
11	Number of citizens who reported that the workshops were a gender-equal environment / Total number of citizens surveyed
12	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda adequately promotes an equal representation of female researchers in the decision-making bodies and/or research-performing organisations / Total number of citizens surveyed
13	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda will contribute to the adoption of new technologies by local governments as a measure to improve their relationship with the citizens they serve / Total number of citizens surveyed
14	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda will increase the social approval and adoption of new smart technologies by embodying ethical standards to their design / Total number of citizens surveyed
15	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda, if materialise, will promote economic growth and spread its fruits fairly across society / Total number of citizens surveyed

RESOURCES Who should you involve in the monitoring activities and what other resources do you need?

Should the people organizing the workshops also be responsible for collecting feedback, or should there be another dedicated team? Would the questionnaires be in paper or digital form? In the latter case, do you need a survey tool? Also, should the collected data be stored in a reporting database?

Team:
Other Resources:

TIMELINE Summarise your key next actions into a timeline to ensure smooth implementation

